

Formation of Unusual Molecular Complexes by Some Organotin(Aryl azo)benzoates

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Triorganotin-*o*-(4-*N,N*-dimethyl amino benzene azo)benzoates are characterised by an unusual ability to form molecular complexes with a wide variety of molecules including saturated hydrocarbons. Formation constants vary from $\sim 10^{-3}$ litre mole $^{-1}$ for the saturated hydrocarbon complexes to $\sim 10^4$ litre mole $^{-1}$ for chloranil complexes. The bathochromic shift of the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition as well as the presence of CT band in nitrobenzene complex suggest these to be of donor-acceptor type, the organotin molecule behaving as the donor. Protonated species are formed by the action of protic solvents on the complexes. Possible reasons for the unusual donor ability is discussed.

FUNCTIONALLY substituted azobenzenes have been extensively used¹⁻³ for the synthesis of triorganotin complexes where the coordination number of the tin atom can be varied from 4 to 7 by using appropriately substituted azobenzene. Even the extremely rare 7-coordinated triorganotin chelates have been prepared using acetoxy substituted azobenzenes⁴. Amongst these group of compounds triorganotin-*o*-(4-*N,N*-dimethyl amino benzene azo)benzoates (I) are unique in their ability to form molecular complexes with almost any type of molecule including unsubstituted alkanes for which no example other than the contact charge transfer complexes (CCT) are known⁵.

IA - R = Ph, R' = H
IB - R = *n*-Bu, R' = H
IC - R = Ph, R' = Me

I

In this paper we briefly discuss the evidences leading to the characterisation of such unusual molecular complexes which opens up the possibility of synthesising more stable complexes involving saturated hydrocarbons.

Experimental

Triorganotin complexes, IA and IB, were prepared by the method described by Majee and Banerjee³.

IC was prepared by stirring at room temperature equimolar mixture of Ph₃SnCl and sodium salt of *o*-(2-methyl, 4-*N,N*-dimethyl aminobenzene azo)benzoic acid in ethanol for about 10 hr. The product was recrystallised from petroleum ether; m.p. 144°, yield 70%.

Methyl ester of *o*-(4-*N,N*-dimethyl aminobenzene azo)benzoic acid (II) was prepared by the method described by Majee and Chakravarti^{3,2}.

All solvents were of Uvasol (E. Merck) grade. Optical densities were measured using a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cells. All measurements were carried at r.t. (27 ± 2°).

All computations were carried on DCM Microsystem 112I and Spectrum-I.

Results and Discussion

Electronic absorption spectra of aryl azo benzenes and their organotin derivatives: The electronic spectra of azobenzene and its derivatives are characterised by two bands, an intense absorption ($\epsilon_{\max} \sim 10^4$) due to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition and a weak to moderate absorption band ($\epsilon_{\max} \sim 600$) at ~ 440 nm due to $n-\pi^*$ transition^{3,6-7}. The later absorption is generally masked under the strong $\pi-\pi^*$ absorption in the azo dyes and related compounds^{1-3,6-11}. Because of this all the functionally substituted azo compounds and their organotin derivatives so far studied show a single strong absorption band in the visible region except when solvent-solute interaction, e.g., H-bonding, solvation of the tin atom or solvent dependent azo-hydrazone tautomeric equilibria^{3,12-16} etc., leads to the formation of new species which are characterised by new absorption bands in the spectrum.

The absorption maxima of the triorganotin-*o*-(4-*N,N*-dimethyl aminobenzene azo)benzoates (I), the corresponding methyl ester (II) and 4-*N,N*-dimethyl amino azo benzene (III) are given in Table I.

TABLE I—ABSORPTION MAXIMA (nm) IN THE SPECTRA OF THE AZO DYES AND THEIR ORGANOTIN DERIVATIVES

Solvent/Solute	IA	IB	II	III
Cyclohexane	405, 470 ^d	395, 470 ^d	400	398 ^a
Carbon tetrachloride	405, 480 ^d	410, 460 ^d	401	—
Benzene	425 ^d , 480	420 ^d , 480	412	410
Acetone	420 ^d , 490	410, 490 ^d	—	411 ^b
Methanol	415, 490 ^d	410, 488 ^d	413	410 ^a
DMSO	415	412	425	—
Pyridine	425	419	420	—

(a) *iso*-octane, (b) ethyl methyl ketone, (c) ethanol, (d) wave length corresponding to the shoulder/inflexion in the spectrum.

Fig. 3. Spectrum of IA in *n*-heptane containing (1) 20, (2) 60 and (3) 90% (v/v) CCl_4 .

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CCl_4 AND NITROBENZENE (A) ON THE INTEGRATED MOLAR ABSORPTIVITIES OF $\pi-\pi^*$ TRANSITIONS OF IA AND IB IN ALKANE

Solute/Solvent	A	Amount of A (% v/v) in solution	Integrated molar absorptivity $\times 10^{-7}$		
			Band 1	Band 2	Total
IA/ <i>n</i> -hexane	nitrobenzene	0	11.96	1.02	12.98
		4	3.22	9.19	12.41
		10	2.41	9.80	12.21
IA/ <i>n</i> -heptane	CCl_4	20	9.89	0.76	10.15
		60	9.04	1.27	10.31
		90	8.44	2.12	10.56
IB/ <i>n</i> -hexane	nitrobenzene	100	5.97	4.13	10.10
		4	3.69	7.80	11.49
		8	2.60	9.97	12.57
IB/ <i>n</i> -heptane	CCl_4	12	2.05	11.00	12.05
		5	12.34	0.75	13.09
		25	12.07	0.90	12.97
		70	11.91	1.10	13.01
		100	10.00	2.87	12.87

respectively, to the complexed and the uncomplexed species.

The approximate constancy of the total integrated absorptivity shows the oscillator strength of the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition in both the species to be the same. This is expected since the longest wavelength absorption band in both the species arises from a slightly perturbed LE transition in the azo molecule bound to the triorganotin group through an ester linkage which is not conjugative. A simple perturbation treatment shows that the transition dipole, hence, the integrated absorptivity, of a LE transition in a weak molecular complex remains unchanged to the first order (Appendix II).

Stoichiometry and formation constants: Determination of the stoichiometry and the formation constant of a molecular complex generally requires the measurement of absorbance in a set of solutions in an inert or non-interacting solvent in which the

concentration of one of the components is varied. The absorbance data can then be treated by one of the several methods available to determine the desired parameters. Although DMSO and pyridine apparently seems to be non-interacting in the present case (rather unusual!) in as much as the organotin compounds show only a single absorption band, these can not be used as a reference solvent because of their immiscibility with saturated hydrocarbons and due to the possibility of solvation of the tin atom which is well known in such system². The following procedure was, therefore, adopted.

Consider 1 : 1 complex formation between a solute D and a reagent A in a solvent S which competes with A.

Assuming the validity of Beer's law, the apparent molar absorptivity ϵ^λ , at a wavelength, λ , is given by

$$\epsilon^\lambda \cdot C_D = \epsilon_D^\lambda [D] + \epsilon_{DS}^\lambda [DS] + \epsilon_{DA}^\lambda [DA] + \epsilon_S^\lambda [S] + \epsilon_A^\lambda [A] \quad \dots (4)$$

where the symbol ϵ_X^λ denotes molar absorptivity of species X and the total concentration, C_D , of the solute is given by

$$C_D = [D] + [DA] + [DS] + \{1 + K_{DA}[A] + K_{DS}[S]\}[D] \quad \dots (5)$$

Since the measurements were done at a wavelength where the solvent and the reagent do not absorb and $[S] \gg C_D$; $[A] \gg C_D$, we obtain from eqns. (4) and (5)

$$\epsilon^\lambda = (\epsilon_D^\lambda + K_{DS} \cdot \epsilon_{DS}^\lambda \cdot C_S) / (1 + K_{DS} \cdot C_S) + K_{DA} \cdot C_A (\epsilon_{DA}^\lambda - \epsilon^\lambda) / (1 + K_{DS} \cdot C_S) \quad \dots (6)$$

where C_S and C_A are the analytical concentrations of S and A respectively.

When the reagent A is a solid and used as a solution in the solvent, S, the solvent concentration remains constant and eqn. (6) can be reduced to the linear form

$$\epsilon^\lambda = \epsilon_{DA}^\lambda - (\epsilon^\lambda - \epsilon_D^\lambda) / (K'_{DA} \cdot C_A) \quad \dots (7)$$

where the apparent formation constant, K'_{DA} , is given by

$$K'_{DA} = K_{DA} / (1 + K_{DS} \cdot C_S) \quad \dots (8)$$

and ϵ_D^λ , the apparent molar absorptivity of the solute in the solvent S is given by

$$\epsilon_D^\lambda = (\epsilon_D^\lambda + K_{DS} \cdot \epsilon_{DS}^\lambda \cdot C_S) / (1 + K_{DS} \cdot C_S) \quad \dots (9)$$

Since ϵ^λ and ϵ_D^λ can be obtained from absorbance data, plot of $(\epsilon^\lambda - \epsilon_D^\lambda) / C_A$ vs ϵ^λ may be used to test the formation of 1 : 1 complex. However, the situation is more complicated in our case since the reagent A being a liquid, e.g., CCl_4 , C_6H_6 etc., any increase in C_A results in concomitant decrease of C_S . Neglecting any change in volume due to mixing, it can be shown that

$$C_S = C_S^0 - a_{SA} \cdot C_A \quad \dots (10)$$

where C_S^0 is concentration of the pure solvent and

$$a_{SA} = M_A \cdot \rho_s / (M_s \cdot \rho_A)$$

where M_A , ρ_A and M_s , ρ_s are the molecular weight and density of A and S respectively.

Using eqn. (10), eqn. (6) can be reduced to the form

$$\epsilon^\lambda = \epsilon - (\epsilon^\lambda - \epsilon_0^\lambda) / K \cdot C_A \quad \dots (11)$$

$$\text{where } \epsilon = (K_{DA} \cdot \epsilon_{DA}^\lambda + K_{DS} \cdot \alpha_{SA} \cdot \epsilon_D^\lambda) / (1 + K_{DS} \cdot C_S^0) \quad \dots (12)$$

$$\text{and } K = (K_{DA} - K_{DS} \cdot \alpha_{SA}) / (1 + K_{DS} \cdot C_S^0) \quad \dots (13)$$

Since C_D is usually kept fixed while C_A is systematically varied, one may use the optical densities, d^λ , instead of the molar absorptivities and plot $(d^\lambda - d_0^\lambda) / C_A$ vs d^λ to test the presence of 1 : 1 complex forming equilibria. A few typical plots for IA using a hydrocarbon as reference solvent are shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The linearity of the plots

Fig. 4. Plot of d^λ vs $(d^\lambda - d_0^\lambda) / C_A$ for IA in cyclohexane containing 5-35% (v/v) benzene at 470 nm (—●—●—), 480 nm (—○—○—) and 490 nm (—○—○—).

Fig. 5. Plot of d^λ vs $(d^\lambda - d_0^\lambda) / C_A$ for IA in cyclohexane containing 10-60% (v/v) toluene at 470 nm (—●—●—), 480 nm (—○—○—) and 490 nm (—○—○—).

and the constancy of the slopes at different wavelengths confirm the formation of 1 : 1 complexes by the organotin compounds. The experimental conditions and the apparent formation constants obtained from the plots are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS AND THE APPARENT FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR SOME IA-S-A SYSTEMS

S	A	$C_D \times 10^3$ (M)	Range of C_A (M)	$K \times 10^{10}$ (litre mole ⁻¹)
Cyclohexane	Nitrobenzene	2.752	0.97-5.84	9.9
Cyclohexane	Benzene	4.876	0.56-8.94	5.1
Cyclohexane	Toluene	2.898	0.94-5.64	3.7
Cyclohexane	<i>m</i> -Xylene	3.213	0.81-4.86	3.3
<i>n</i> -Pentane	Benzene	4.876	0.56-3.94	6.3
		2.436	1.12-6.76	6.0
<i>n</i> -Hexane	Benzene	6.932	0.56-3.94	7.2
<i>n</i> -Heptane	Benzene	4.876	0.56-3.94	7.4
		2.208	1.12-6.76	6.7
<i>i</i> -Octane	Benzene	3.569	1.12-6.76	6.9
		2.137	1.12-6.76	5.1
<i>n</i> -Heptane	CCl ₄	5.511	1.03-7.24	8.2×10^4
CCl ₄	Chloranil	5.511	$0.44-1.62 \times 10^{-3}$	

(a) Average of the values calculated from the plots of data at three different wave lengths.

Though the linearity of the plots and the constancy of the calculated values of K confirm the formation of molecular complexes and its stoichiometry, the evaluation of the true formation constants require the use of a truly inert solvent ($K_{DS} = 0$) which is, unfortunately, not feasible experimentally in our case. To overcome this difficulty we therefore used a more direct approach based on the constancy of the integrated absorptivity of a LE transition in a weak complex which, in our case, is confirmed experimentally (Table 3) as well as theoretically (Appendix II).

Since the integrated molar absorptivities of the $\pi - \pi^*$ transition in the complexed and the uncomplexed species are the same, the areas under the corresponding absorption bands, i.e., the integrated absorbances, A_{DA} and A_D are proportional to the concentrations of the species DA and D respectively. Thus,

$$K_{DA} = [DA] / ([D] \cdot [A]) \approx A_{DA} / (A_D \cdot C_A) \quad \dots (14)$$

because $[A] \approx C_A$ since $[D] \ll C_A$.

Using the integrated absorbances of the two bands obtained through a gaussian analysis (Appendix I) of the absorption curves in a given solvent, the formation constants were calculated through eqn. (14). The values are given in Table 5. A comparison of the values given in Tables 4 and 5 shows the apparent formation constants to be lower, even when the reference solvent is a saturated hydrocarbon which are considered to be inert solvents, than the formation constants determined through eqn. (14). Eqn. (13) which relates the apparent formation constant with the true formation constant, and the formation constant of the solvent-solute

TABLE 5—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES OF I WITH DIFFERENT MOLECULES (A)

A	$K_{DA} \times 10^4 (\text{litre mole}^{-1})$		
	IA	IB	IC
Chloranil	1.39×10^4	3.0×10^4	
Nitrobenzene	21.8	17.9	
Benzene	9.2	4.9	6.2
Toluene	9.0		
Acetone	9.0	2.2	
<i>m</i> -Xylene	8.6		
Carbon tetrachloride	6.7	2.8	
Acetonitrile	6.2		
<i>i</i> -Octane	1.6	0.88	1.4
<i>n</i> -Heptane	1.5	0.98	1.7
<i>n</i> -Pentane	1.1	0.72	
<i>n</i> -Hexane	0.98	0.56	1.9
Cyclohexane	0.92	0.86	

complex, K_{DS} , then requires K_{DS} to be finite even in hydrocarbon solvents. For example, inserting the values of appropriate formation constants from Tables 4 and 5 in eqn. (13), a value of ~ 0.02 litre/mole is obtained for the IA-cyclohexane complex, the value obtained by direct method being ~ 0.01 litre/mole. In view of the large uncertainties associated with the parameters obtained through the use of eqn. (11), the agreement is quite satisfactory. Because of the low values of the formation constants a knowledge of the errors involved and the reliability of the calculated values are crucial in deciding whether or not the complexes should be regarded as collision or contact complexes. This point is examined in Appendix III.

Nature of the complexes: Since the solvent-solute interaction with the organotin compounds, I, takes place even in non polar and aprotic solvents, H-bonding and solvation of the tin atom through coordination can be ruled out. The increase in the value of K_{DA} for a given organotin compound (D) with different A in the sequence: A=alkane $\ll$ CCl₄ $\ll$ xylene $\sim$ toluene $\sim$ benzene $\ll$ nitrobenzene $\ll$ chloranil suggests a correlation with the acceptor strength of A. Again, the spectrum of I-nitrobenzene system in *n*-hexane shows a new absorption band at ~ 376 - 388 nm in addition to the ~ 490 nm π - π^* transition of the complexed species (Fig.6). This band may be reasonably assigned to a charge-transfer (CT) transition of the I-nitrobenzene complex. The bathochromic shift and the increase in its intensity with nitrobenzene concentration which increases the solvent polarity and thereby stabilizes the more polar CT state relative to the ground state, supports this assignment. The complexes are, presumably, of donor-acceptor type in which the organotin molecule acts as the donor. However, no such CT band is found with other reagents. This is not surprising because the CT transition is expected to occur at much lower wavelength with benzene, toluene etc. and may be completely masked under their absorption bands. In case of I-alkane complexes, the CT state will definitely lie very much above the ground state due to the nonavailability of any low lying acceptor orbitals in alkanes thereby making it inaccessible.

Fig. 6. Spectrum of IA in *n*-hexane containing (1) 4, (2) 10 and (3) 15% (v/v) nitrobenzene.

On the other hand, the complexes, atleast in some cases, may be formed through Van der Waals or dipole-dipole interactions which play important role in many weak complexes¹⁸⁻²⁵. However, the bathochromic shift of the π - π^* transition on complexation suggests a significant contribution from the polar structure $D^{\delta+}A^{\delta-}$ because the lowering of the π^* -level in azo dyes is generally indicative of lowering of electron density in the molecule⁶. For example, the protonated species, formed in acid medium, show a bathochromic shift of ~ 50 - 100 nm in most cases^{8-11,26-29}.

The small values of the formation constants ($K < 0.1$) are often regarded as an indication of collision or CCT (contact charge transfer) complexes³⁰. Murrell³¹, on the other hand, has shown such distinction to be wholly unnecessary when the solvation is taken into account. In fact, the concept of CCT in solution is nebulous when it is based on the magnitude of the formation constant only^{30,32}. The existence of a chemically distinguishable species in the present case can be convincingly demonstrated by the effect of protic solvents, e.g., methanol. For example, the addition of methanol to a solution of I in any other aprotic solvent brings about the following changes in its spectrum: (i) a new absorption band appears with concomitant decrease in the intensity of original absorption bands due to the complexed (DA) and uncomplexed species (D). The position of the new band depends only on the organotin molecule, D (Table 6) (ii) at high methanol concentration ($> 30\%$ v/v) all the curves pass through an isobestic point (Fig. 7) and (iii) the intensity of the new absorption reversibly increases with decrease of pH showing this to be associated with the protonated species (Fig. 7).

A quantitative study of the effect of pH on the organotin compounds in H₂O-methanol mixtures of

Fig. 7. Spectrum of IO in pure methanol (2) and in presence of 80% (v/v) $n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{14}$ (3), CCl_4 (4), C_6H_6 (5), Chloranil (6), 2 equiv. HCl (---), NH_4OH (1).

TABLE 6—POSITION OF THE LONGEST WAVELENGTH BAND IN SOME D-A-MeOH SYSTEMS

Compound	IA	IB	IC
λ_{max} (nm)	492	488	508

different compositions confirms the presence of the equilibrium :

Assuming the validity of Beer's law, it is possible to deduce the following relation for this equilibrium :

$$\epsilon^\lambda = \epsilon_{\text{DH}^+}^\lambda - (\epsilon^\lambda - \epsilon_{\text{D}}^\lambda) \cdot 10^{-p\text{H}} / K_b \quad \dots (16)$$

were ϵ^λ , $\epsilon_{\text{DH}^+}^\lambda$ and $\epsilon_{\text{D}}^\lambda$ are respectively, the molar extinction of the solution, DH^+ and D at the wavelength, λ .

Experimental verification of the Beer's law and eqn. (16) both confirm the formation of DH^+ and yields the value of the basicity constant, K_b . The pK_b values of the relevant azo compounds in 100% methanol obtained by extrapolation are given in Table 7.

TABLE 7— pK_b IN PURE METHANOL OF SOME AZO DYES AND THEIR ORGANOTIN DERIVATIVES

Compound	pK_b
IA	-6.27
IB	-6.10
II	-2.60
IV	-3.10
o-(4-N,N-dimethyl amino benzene azo)-benzoic acid	-5.90
Azobenzene	-2.90 ^a
4-N,N-dimethyl amino azo benzene	-3.50 ^b

(a) Ref. 11, (b) Ref. 26.

Interestingly, the same protonated species, as shown by the absorption spectrum as well as the effect of pH, is formed by the addition of an alkane, CCl_4 , ether, benzene etc. or an acceptor like chloranil, DDQ etc. The increase in $[\text{DH}^+]$ with increase in $[\text{A}]$ in methanol, even when A is an alkane (Fig. 8) can be explained only through the formation of a species involving D and A which is

Fig. 8. Spectrum of IA in (1) pure methanol and in presence of (2) 10, (3) 20 and (4) 40% (v/v) cyclohexane in methanol.

then solvolyzed by the protic solvent as shown below.

Although the formation of A.OMe^- in eqn. (17b) has been invoked to balance it, evidence for this species has now been obtained when A is a strong acceptor e.g., chloranil. The difference spectrum of D-chloranil-MeOH system and D- DH^+ system (obtained by addition of dil. HCl to methanolic solution of D till the absorption due to DH^+ becomes identical in both the systems) shows an absorption at ~ 42 nm which is absent in the spectrum of chloranil in the same solvent (Fig. 9). Since the difference spectrum is independent of the nature of D, it is associated only with the chloranil containing species. A similar absorption is found in the spectrum of chloranil in presence of Na-methoxide and is, presumably, due to $[\text{chloranil-OMe}^-]$ complex since many anions are known to form CT complexes with chloranil²²⁻²⁵.

The effect of methanol thus strongly supports the formation of molecular complexes by the organotin compounds of type I with all types of molecules including the alkanes, albeit, very weak. Preliminary studies on the effect of temperature on this system showed no detectable change in the optical density for a $\sim 10^\circ$ change in temperature. The maximum error involved in K which is $\sim 6\%$ (Appendix III) then puts an upper limit of 1 Kcal/mole to the heat of formation. Such a small stabilization of the ground state coupled with a

Fig. 9. Spectrum of chloranil in methanol (1), the difference spectrum of D-chloranil-MeOH system (2) and spectrum of chloranil in methanol containing 1 equiv. NaOMe (3).

considerable bathochromic shift of the π - π^* transition therefore suggests greater stabilization of the excited state on complexation.

Structure and donor properties of the organotin compounds: The unusual donor ability is lost in *p*-carboxy compounds (IV) or in compounds in which the amino group is replaced by other groups (V).

The loss of donor ability of I in pyridine and DMSO in which 5-coordinate organotin-*o*-(aryl azo)-benzoates undergo facile solvolysis through cleavage of the chelate ring as well as in the *p*-carboxy compound, V, where no chelate ring is present in contrast to the *o*-carboxy compound (VI)^{1,2}, shows this ring to be essential for the unusual donor ability.

This is probably due to the resonating structure VII which makes the -COO group electron rich in such molecules resulting in high donor ability. The importance of structure VII is shown by the

relatively low asymmetric OCO stretch in such compounds ($\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)¹. The high polarity of the Sn-O bond, estimated to be $\sim 51\%$ from Pauling's electronegativities^{8,9}, enhances the electron density on the -COO group. The fact that only highly basic molecules ($pK_b \sim -6.0$, see Table 7) are able to show such unusual donor ability supports this. Since the structure VII is certain to make greater contribution to the excited state than the ground state, the excited state is expected to be more stabilized on complexation in agreement with the observed bathochromic shift of the π - π^* transition.

The formation of DH^+ by the action of methanol on the molecular complexes (DA) can be explained by the initial formation of H-bond with the O-atom of the -COO group which attains higher effective electronegativity in the complex due to partial removal of electron density from D to A, followed by a rearrangement to the final species as shown below.

While much work remains to be done before the unusual donor ability of the organotin compounds of type I can be fully understood and explored, the present investigations open up the possibility of preparing complexes of saturated hydrocarbons, which was highlighted by Prof. Chatt in his lecture "25 years of the ICCS: Prospect and Retrospect"¹⁰.

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Appendix I

Resolution of absorption curves :

The absorption curves were represented by analytical function of the type :

$$A_{\nu} = \sum A_{max}^k \text{Exp} \left[-b \left\{ \left(\nu - \nu_{max}^k \right) / \Delta \nu_{1/2}^k \right\}^2 \right] \quad \dots (A1)$$

where A_{ν} is the absorbance at frequency ν ; ν_{max}^k , A_{max}^k and $\Delta \nu_{1/2}^k$ are, respectively, the position of the maximum, absorbance at the maximum and halfwidth of the k th band; b is a constant. The

oscillator strength, f, of the band system is given by

$$f = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} \int_{band} A_{\nu} \cdot d\nu = 4.60 \times 10^{-9} \sum_k A_{max}^k \cdot \Delta \nu_{1/2}^k \quad (A2)$$

The experimental curves were fitted by an iterative process in which the parameters A_{max}^k , ν_{max}^k and $\Delta \nu_{1/2}^k$ were varied till the error was minimized (least square technique)¹⁷.

Appendix II

Transition moment of a LE transition in a weak molecular complex :

Consider a LE transition $\psi_{k(D)} \rightarrow \psi_{i(D)}$ in the component, D, of a weak molecular complex, DA. Using perturbation theory¹⁸, we have

$$\psi_{k(D)} = \psi_{k(D)}^0 + \lambda \sum_{s(\neq k)} \frac{\langle \psi_{k(D)}^0 | h' | \psi_{s(A)}^0 \rangle}{E_k^0 - E_s^0} \psi_{s(A)}^0 + \quad (A3)$$

where $\psi_{k(D)}^0$ and $\psi_{s(A)}^0$'s are the MO's of the separated components D and A respectively and h' is the perturbation due to complexation, λ being the perturbation parameter¹⁸.

In a weak complex, perturbation being small, terms higher than the first order can be neglected. The transition moment is therefore given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi_{i(D)} | \mu | \psi_{k(D)} \rangle &= \langle \psi_{k(D)}^0 | \mu | \psi_{i(D)}^0 \rangle \\ &+ \left[\sum_{s(\neq k)} \frac{\langle \psi_{k(D)}^0 | h' | \psi_{s(A)}^0 \rangle \langle \psi_{s(A)}^0 | \mu | \psi_{i(D)}^0 \rangle}{E_k^0 - E_s^0} \right. \\ &\left. + \sum_{s(\neq i)} \frac{\langle \psi_{i(D)}^0 | h' | \psi_{s(A)}^0 \rangle \langle \psi_{k(D)}^0 | \mu | \psi_{s(A)}^0 \rangle}{E_i^0 - E_s^0} \right] \quad \dots (A4) \end{aligned}$$

Since $\psi_{k(D)}^0$ and $\psi_{i(D)}^0$ are localized on D while $\psi_{s(A)}^0$'s are localized on A, all matrix elements between these vanish in ZDO approximation which is correct to first order in overlap¹⁸. Hence,

$$\langle \psi_{i(D)} | \mu | \psi_{k(D)} \rangle = \langle \psi_{k(D)}^0 | \mu | \psi_{i(D)}^0 \rangle \quad \dots (A5)$$

showing the transition moment of a LE transition remains unchanged, to a good approximation, on complexation.

Appendix III

Relative error in the estimation of formation constants :

For a gaussian curve

$$A_{\nu} = A_{max} \text{Exp}[-a(\nu - \nu_{max})^2] \quad \dots (A6)$$

the integrated absorbance, A, is given by

$$A = \int_{band} A_{\nu} \cdot d\nu = \sqrt{\pi/a} \cdot A_{max} \quad \dots (A7)$$

The relative error, $\Delta A/A$, is then obtained by differentiation,

$$\Delta A/A = (\Delta A_{max}/A_{max} - \Delta a/2a) \quad (A8)$$

Analysis of the absorbance data calculated from gaussian functions (A6) shows the maximum error in A_{max} and a obtained from least square fit to be $\pm 2\%$ giving a maximum limit of $\pm 3\%$ error in the integrated absorbance data. Therefore, the relative error in the formation constants calculated by the use of eqn. (14) is given by

$$\Delta K_{D_A}/K_{D_A} = |\Delta A_D/A_{D_A}| + |\Delta A_D/A_D| \doteq 6\%$$

Unlike the Benesi-Hildebrand equation³⁹ or its variants^{40,41} where linearization is achieved through variables which often involve reciprocal of optical densities so that large errors frequently creep into the estimated values of K and ϵ_{max} , particularly for $K < 0.1$, making the results suspect, the present method is free from such sources of errors so that the estimated values of K_{D_A} can be used with confidence.